

Effect of Instructional Conversation Strategy on Achievement in Basic Science and Technology among Secondary School Students in Mkpato Enin Local Government

Robson, Blessing Okon¹

Email: blezokonrobson@gmail.com

Tel: 07039287469

Babayemi, John Olakunle¹

Email: babayemioluwole@gmail.com

Tel: 08038421726

Umanah, Felicia Ime¹

Email: feliciaumanah@aksu.edu.ng

¹Tel: 07088885603

Department of Science Education, Faculty of Education, Akwa Ibom State University, Akwa Ibom State, Nigeria.

Abstract

The study determined effect of instructional conversation strategy on achievement in basic science and technology among secondary school students in Mkpato Enin Local Government. Quasi-experimental research design, specifically pre-test, post-test control group design was adopted for the study. The population of the study comprised of 1645 (809 males and 836 female) Junior Secondary School class three (JS III) Public Secondary School students during the 2022/2023 academic session from all the sixteen (16) public secondary schools in Mkpato Enin Local Government. A total of 168 (63 male and 105 female) students using an intact class were used as sample for the study. Two research questions and corresponding hypotheses guided the study. The instrument validated and used was Basic Science and Technology Achievement Test, BSTSAT and Kuder Richardson KR-20 estimate was used to determine the reliability index which yielded 0.75. Data collected were analyzed using descriptive statistics to answer the research questions and ANCOVA to test the hypotheses at 0.05 level of significance. The results showed that instructional strategies had a significant main effect on students' posttest achievement scores [$F_{(1,168)} = 40.622$; $p < .05$], there was no significant influence of gender on students' academic achievement [$F_{(1,168)} = .296$; $p > .05$]. The study concluded that instructional conversation strategy improved students' academic achievement. It was recommended among others that in order to improve male and female students' achievement in Basic Science and Technology, instructional conversations teaching strategy should be adopted by the teacher in secondary schools.

Keywords: Instructional Conversations, Gender, Academic Achievement, Basic Science and Technology

Introduction

The teaching and learning of science and technology in Nigeria starts from acquiring knowledge, skills and attitude in Basic Science and Technology in Primary and Secondary schools. Therefore, the way Basic Science and Technology is taught in schools determines to a large extent, the achievement of curricular objectives for the target learners and overall scientific and technological attainments of the nation at large. Babayemi, Akpan and Emah (2018) observed that students have difficulty in learning scientific concepts. The difficulty encountered in the learning of Basic Science and Technology may be ascribed to how the teaching of the subject is done by the subject teachers. Babayemi *et al.*, (2018) identified science teachers as the key factors in students' learning. These researchers submitted that teachers must be equipped with appropriate strategies to proffer solution to the problem of any perceived difficult concepts. This seems to reduce the difficulty encountered during learning.

Federal Ministry of Education [FME] (2013) remarked that the society is faced with large number of teachers that are unable to manage the classroom of the 21st century and concluded that this state is counterproductive, antithetical to growth and development. The world outside the classroom keeps changing because of the innovations in science and technology and it is necessary for the classroom environment to undergo corresponding change so as to be able to meet the needs and aspirations of the learners. Many learners tend to become more sophisticated and highly proficient in the use of ICT and other media than their teachers. Teachers therefore need to seriously update their skills and pedagogies so as to be able to face the present

Effect of Instructional Conversation ... (Robson, et. al., 2023) DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10681420>

challenges in the classroom. What is worrisome about these challenges common in research reports is the low academic achievement in schools (Babalola, 2018).

Profile of Basic Science (Basic Science and Technology) results as reported by Babayemi and Akinsola (2014) was not consistent over the years. If this abysmal failure in Basic Science and Technology follows the same trends subsequently, the realization of national objectives in scientific and technological developments would definitely be in jeopardy. The way science teaching and learning is done in schools need to be revisited. Basic Science and Technology teachers are expected to be flexible in the use of pedagogy so as to be able to meet the needs of diverse learners in science classrooms. In line with this, Afuwape and Olugbuyi (2019) observed poor academic performance of students in Basic science and Technology and recommended the use of activity package-based instruction to eradicate the menace.

There are innovations in methodology. Murugesan (2019) identified innovative teaching strategies that could be adopted for students' learning. These are: blended learning, embodied learning, learning by doing science, computational thinking, crossover learning, learning through argumentation, word wall and instructional conversations among others. Teaching pedagogy is a basic element of an effective teaching. This means that the right choice of pedagogy is very important for the teaching and learning to be effective. Teachers should see the need to consider what pedagogy will be appropriate for a particular curricular content and the particular category of learners. Hence, the need to conduct further research on strategies that seem to promote students' learning of science in a motivated environment such as instructional conversations and word wall teaching strategies. Girenton and Zucker (2013) viewed instructional conversations as planned discussions with small groups of children where teachers improve students' collaborative reasoning by using challenging questions which necessitate students to use complex language to relay their experiences, knowledge and opinions. Lending credence to this, Babayemi and Utibe (2017) pointed out that in every day-to-day activity (including class activities), communication is necessary and without an effective communication, the essence of discussion and the active purpose of a dialogue are forfeited. Ouboumerrad (2016) laying great emphasis on inter-personal conversation recommended and stressed that meaningful conversations should become essential activities in the classroom.

Ordinarily, a good instructional conversation might appear as "simply and excellent discussion conducted by a teacher and a group of students". Most people have a reasonably intuitive sense of what such a discussion might be like. It is, first, interesting and engaging. It is about an idea or a concept that has meaning and relevance for students. It has focus that, while it might shift as the discussion evolves, remains discernible throughout. There is a high level of participation, without undue domination by any individual, particularly the teacher. Students engage in extended discussions-with the teacher and among themselves. Gender issue in educational and social research remains the concern of researchers. Hence, there is the need to consider gender germane to this research. In this study, gender is categorised as either male or female learners. Gender has attracted the attention of researchers and has different research views and reports especially with reference to academic achievement. Calsmith (2010) explained that, the influence of gender and differences in academic achievement is a complex task, thus many studies appear to be contradictory. A tremendous amount of work has been done in an attempt to find out potential causes of differences between girls' and boys' academic performance in science and this has clearly demonstrated that male students are superior to their female counterparts in qualitative courses. Maccoby (2013) for example, pointed out that girls are conforming, suggestible, dependent on the opinions of others. The traits in turn have been adduced to dependency, inability to complete a set of tasks. Maccoby then suggests that, these same traits in females might also account for their superior performance on tests involving analytic thinking and spatial abilities.

Zhang, Zhao and Kong (2019) notes that female students are lower in Mathematics and spatial tasks and on specific abilities related to problem solving. Giofre, Allen, Caviola and Toffalini (2022) contended that there are gender differences in intellectual functioning which accounted for the differences in performance. Ayayo (2017) attributed the differences in performance between boys and girls to the school, general intelligence of girls higher than that of boys but the position gradually reversed with the findings. Therefore, this study determined effect of instructional conversation strategy on achievement in Basic Science and Technology among secondary school students in Mkpat Enin Local Government.

Objectives of The Study

The study aimed generally to determine effect of instructional conversation strategy on achievement in Basic Science and Technology among secondary school students in Mkpat Enin Local Government. Specifically, the study:

1. Determine academic achievement of students taught Basic Science and Technology using instructional conversation and those exposed to lecture teaching method in Mkpat Enin Local Government Area.

Effect of Instructional Conversation ... (Robson, et. al., 2023) DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10681420>

2. Determine academic achievement of male and female students taught Basic Science and Technology using instructional conversation in Mkpato Enin Local Government Area.

Research Questions

The following research questions guided study:

1. What is the mean academic achievement scores of students taught Basic Science and Technology using instructional conversation and those exposed to lecture teaching method in Mkpato Enin Local Government Area?
2. What is the mean academic achievement scores of male and female students taught Basic Science and Technology using instructional conversation in Mkpato Enin Local Government Area?

Hypotheses

The following hypotheses were tested at 0.05 alpha level.

1. There is no significant difference between the mean academic achievement scores of students taught Basic Science and Technology using instructional conversation and those exposed to lecture teaching method in Mkpato Enin Local Government Area.
2. There is no significant difference between the mean academic achievement scores of male and female students taught Basic Science and Technology using instructional conversation in Mkpato Enin Local Government Area.

Methodology

Quasi-experimental research design, specifically pre-test, post-test control group design was adopted for the study. The population of the study comprised of 1645 (809 male and 836 female) Junior Secondary School class three (JS III) Public Secondary School students during the 2022/2023 academic session from all the sixteen (16) public secondary schools in Mkpato Enin Local Government. A total of 168 (63 male and 105 female) students using an intact class were used as sample for the study. Three instruments were used and validated by the researcher to collect data for the study. The instruments are: Basic Science and Technology Achievement Test (BSTSAT), Teachers' Instructional Guide for Instructional Conversations Teaching Strategy (TIGICTS) and Teachers' Instructional Guide for Group Taught without Instructional Conversations Teaching Strategy (TIGGTICTS). Basic Science and Technology Students' Achievement Test, BSTSAT was designed by the researcher. The test was divided into two sections: A and B. Section A covered the personal data of the participants which are gender and name of school; Section B contained twenty (20) multiple choice items with five options (A-E) from which participants selected the correct answer. Each correct response attracted one mark while an incorrect response was awarded zero.

Teachers' instructional guide for instructional conversations teaching strategy (TIGICTS) was also developed by the researcher. It contains the lessons for the four weeks of treatment. The general features of this guide were: subject, class, Instructional strategy, topic, sub-topic, duration, initial previous knowledge, instructional objectives, reference book, Introduction, presentation and evaluation. The specific features of this guide were: small group activity, individual activity. Researcher also developed Teachers' Instructional Guide for Group Taught without Instructional Conversations Teaching Strategy (TIGGTICTS). It contains lessons for four weeks of the treatment. The general information on the guide was: subject, class, topic, sub-topic, duration, instructional objectives, previous knowledge, instructional aids and reference book. The specific features of the guide were teachers' activities which are: daily reviews, assessment of pupils previous works, brief introduction, teacher presenting learning tasks in the usual traditional way, evaluation and assignment.

The initial draft of twenty-five multiple choice items of Basic Science and Technology Achievement Test (BSTAT) were given to experts for peer review and two lecturers in the Department of Science Education, Faculty of Education, Akwa Ibom State University, Akwa Ibom State who were experts in the field of Science Education. This was done to ascertain the face and internal consistency of the instruments. Twenty (20) items out of 25 for BSTAT were recommended. BSTAT was later trial-tested on 30 students in a secondary school that was not selected for the main study. The data collected were analysed using Kuder Richardson KR-20 estimate which yielded the reliability coefficients of 0.75. In each of the schools, the researcher obtained permission from the school authority and students for the administrations of the instruments. The treatments were done using the instructional guides. Pre-test and Post-test administered before and after the treatment. The data were collated for data analysis. Data collected were analyzed using mean and Analysis of Covariance (ANCOVA) of the posttest achievement scores of students by treatment and gender with the respective pretest scores used as covariates.

Results

Effect of Instructional Conversation ... (Robson, et. al., 2023) DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10681420>

Research Question 1

What is the mean academic achievement scores of students taught Basic Science and Technology using instructional conversation and those exposed to lecture teaching method in Mkpato Enin Local Government Area?

Table 1: Estimated adjusted Means of Post-Achievement Scores by Instructional Strategies

Instructional Strategies	Adjusted Mean	Std. Error
Students taught with Instructional Conversations Teaching Strategy	16.59	.251
Students taught with lecture teaching method	13.59	.397

Table 1 revealed that students in the instructional conversations teaching strategy group had the highest adjusted posttest mean achievement scores ($\bar{x} = 16.59$) while students taught with lecture teaching method had the least adjusted mean achievement score ($\bar{x} = 13.59$). The difference was high.

Fig. 1: Chart Showing Achievement According to Instructional Strategies

Research Question

What is the mean academic achievement scores of male and female students taught Basic Science and Technology using instructional conversation in Mkpato Enin Local Government Area?

Table 2: Estimated Marginal Means of Post-achievement by Gender

Gender	Adjusted Mean	Std. Error
Male	14.97	.336
Female	15.22	.329

Table 2 revealed that female students had higher post achievement mean score ($\bar{x} = 15.22$) while the male students had lower post achievement mean score ($\bar{x} = 14.97$). It shows that the female achievement score was different from their female counterpart. This influence on their mean scores was small. Both male and female Basic Science and Technology students had close mean academic achievement. This implies that there was difference in the mean academic achievement scores of male and female students taught Basic Science and Technology using instructional conversation in Mkpato Enin Local Government Area.

Hypotheses 1

There is no significant difference between the mean academic achievement scores of students taught Basic Science and Technology using instructional conversation and those exposed to lecture teaching method in Mkpato Enin Local Government Area.

Effect of Instructional Conversation ... (Robson, et. al., 2023) DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10681420>

Table 3: Posttest Achievement Scores of Students by Instructional Strategies

Source	Type III Sum of Squares	Df	Mean Square	F	Sig.	Partial Eta Squared
Corrected Model	584.880	12	48.740	10.231	.000	.442
Intercept	3600.204	1	3600.204	755.732	.000	.830
Pre-Achievement	8.659	1	8.659	1.818	.180	.012
Gender	1.409	1	1.409	.296	.587	.002
Verbal Ability	95.011	2	47.505	9.972	.000	.114
Instructional strategies	193.518	1	193.518	40.622	.000	.208
Gender x Verbal Ability	3.961	2	1.981	.416	.661	.005
Gender x instructional strategies	.799	1	.799	.168	.683	.001
Verbal Ability x instructional strategies	3.116	2	1.558	.327	.722	.004
Gender x Verbal Ability x instructional strategies	1.258	2	.629	.132	.876	.002
Error	738.399	155	4.764			
Total	42027.000	168				
Corrected Total	1323.280	167				

a. R Squared = .442 (Adjusted R Squared = .399)

Table 3 reveals that instructional strategies had a significant main effect on students' posttest achievement scores [$F_{(1,168)} = 40.622$; $p < .05$; partial eta squared = .208]. The effect size of 20.8% was fair. The null hypothesis is therefore rejected. This means that There is significant difference between the mean academic achievement scores of students taught Basic Science and Technology using instructional conversation and those exposed to lecture teaching method in Mkpato Enin Local Government Area.

Hypothesis 2

There is no significant difference between the mean academic achievement scores of male and female students taught Basic Science and Technology using instructional conversation in Mkpato Enin Local Government Area.

Table 3 reveals that there is no significant influence of gender on students' academic achievement [$F_{(1,168)} = .296$; $p > .05$; partial eta squared = .002]. Hypothesis 2 was therefore accepted. This implies that there was no significant difference between the mean academic achievement scores of male and female students taught Basic Science and Technology using instructional conversation in Mkpato Enin Local Government Area.

Discussion of Findings

The result obtained revealed that instructional strategies had a significant effect on students' achievement in Basic Science and Technology. This means that there was a significant difference in the mean achievement scores of students exposed to instructional conversations teaching strategy and those taught with lecture teaching method. Students in the instructional conversations teaching strategy group had the highest adjusted post-test mean achievement scores while students taught with lecture teaching method had the least adjusted mean achievement score. The results obtained here could be because children are motivated by an atmosphere where they are allowed to talk, ask questions and expect a satisfactory response from a more knowledgeable person. They are allowed to share their experiences as they relate to the scientific concepts under discussion during the instructional processes.

The result from this study lends credence to Ghaffari and Fatemi's (2016) study which investigated the impact of instructional conversation on oral autonomy of Iranian English as Foreign Language (EFL) Learner. The findings revealed significant difference in the performance of students taught reading comprehension using instructional conversation method. The study further revealed that students from both groups made appreciable gain in the pre-test. The study concluded and

Effect of Instructional Conversation ... (Robson, et. al., 2023) DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10681420>

encouraged teachers to adopt a thematic integrated approach (combining the instructional conversation method and the vocabulary method) since both methods could complement each other, if effectively used.

The results from this study differs from earlier study by Hendy and Cuevas (2020) who examined the effectiveness of the Instructional Conversations (ICs) teaching method on elementary-aged English Language Learning (ELLs) students. Specifically, how ICs impact student academic achievement, academic language usage, and student engagement. Results indicated that ICs did not lead to an increase of academic achievement or academic language usage when compared to students taught through traditional instruction. Results did show that engagement increased when using ICs taught. With an increase in engagement combined with a decrease in academic acquisition, results suggest that ICs should be used with caution when teaching content related material.

The results obtained showed that the effect of gender was not significant on students' achievement. Female students had higher mean while the male students had lower mean). It shows that the female achievement score was different from their female counterpart but the difference in their mean scores was not statistically significant. Both male and female Basic Science and Technology students had similar academic achievement. The findings of this study could probably be attributed to the fact that in Nigeria, the common medium of communication used in schools from primary to tertiary institutions is English Language which would have served as background support for both male and female students.

Previous researchers have reported similar finding. Kola (2013) analysed gender achievement in physics in colleges of education, Nigeria and found no relationship between male and female achievement in Physics. The study concluded that students' achievement in physics in College of Education has no gender bias. Ani *et al.* (2016) examined effect of gender on Basic Science students' academic achievement in secondary schools. The result showed that gender (male/female) had no significant effect on students' achievement in Basic Science. In a related work in Basic Science, Babayemi and Ahmed (2019) in their work on effect of enhanced conventional lecture method and gender on students' achievement in Basic Science, the result showed that there was no significant effect of gender on achievement. Umanah and Sunday (2022) examined crossword puzzle, flashcards teaching strategies and senior secondary school students' academic performance in Chemistry. the study concluded that was not a significant determinant of students' academic performance. It can therefore be concluded that gender of students whether male or female, does not seem to have any influence on the effectiveness of any of the treatment employed in the study.

Conversely, Olagunju and Babayemi (2014) examined the effect of crossword-Picture puzzle (CPP) teaching strategy and gender on students' achievement in Basic Science. Gender had significant main effect on achievement score. A related study on gender by Babayemi (2019) investigated cognitive style and gender as predictors of students' academic performance in Basic Science and Technology in Mkpato Enin Local Government Area, Akwa Ibom State, Nigeria. The findings showed that there was significant difference in the performance of male and female Basic Science and Technology Students with reflective cognitive style and those with impulsive cognitive style.

Conclusion

The study has determined effect of instructional conversation strategy on achievement in basic science and technology among secondary school students in Mkpato Enin Local Government. The results from the study serve as an eye opener to Basic science and Technology teachers on the potential of students' conversations during instructional processes. Instructional conversations, from the findings of the study, improved students' academic achievement. This means that instructional conversation was very effective to teach Basic Science and Technology. The study also revealed that if students are exposed to the same appropriate teaching and learning strategy, both boys and girls can perform in the same way. The teaching strategy/method to be used by the teacher needs to cater for the instructional needs of both boys and girls for their learning gains.

Recommendations

Based on the findings of this study, the following recommendations were made.

1. Teachers should use instructional conversation teaching strategy to teach Basic Science and Technology concepts in secondary schools. This will improve students' academic achievement.
2. To encourage both boys and girls' participation in science especially Basic Science and Technology, instructional conversation teaching strategy that would improve their achievement should be used.
3. Curriculum planners at all levels, should look into the curriculum and adopt instructional conversation teaching strategy in classroom so as to be able to meet the challenges of communication interest of 21st century learners.

Effect of Instructional Conversation ... (Robson, et. al., 2023) DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10681420>

References

- Afuwape, M. O., & Olugbuyi, A. L. (2019). Eradicating poor achievement in basic science and technology through learning activity package: how do students behave in Nigeria? *Journal of Education in Black Sea Region*, 5(1),15–25. *And Methods in Education (IOSR-JRME)*, 4(4), 08-13.
- Ani, M.I., Obodo, A.C., Ikwueze, C.C. &Tafi, F.I. (2021). Effect of gender on basic science students' academic achievement in secondary schools. *Unizik Journal of Educational Research and Policy Studies*, 9, 36-43.
- Ayayo, O. (2017). Effect of gender attitude on academic performance in science: an unpublished M. Ed Dissertation, University of Calabar.
- Babalola, G.T. (2018). Instructional congruence, know-want-learn strategies and students' learning outcomes in basic science in Oyo State, Nigeria. *An unpublished PhD thesis, University of Ibadan.*
- Babayemi J. O. Akpan I. F. &Emah, J. S. (2018). Investigating difficult concepts in basic science and technology curriculum concepts in basic science and technology curriculum for solving energy and power problem for sustainable national development. *CARD International Journal of Education Research and Management Technology*, 3 (1), 11-17.
- Babayemi, J.O &Akinsola, M.K (2014). Effects of crossword-picture puzzle teaching strategy and mental ability on students' achievement in basic science in southwestern Nigeria. *IOSR (International Organization of Scientific Research) Journal of Research*
- Babayemi, J.O. & Ahmed, A.A. (2019). Effects of enhanced conventional lecture method and gender on students' achievement in basic science. *Journal of Contemporary Education Research (JCER)*, 13 (6), 242-256.
- Babayemi, J.O. &Utibe, U.J. (2017). Communicating research findings in basic science and technology for technological development. *Matter: International Journal of Science And Technology*, 3 (1), 1 – 15.
- Babayemi, J.O. (2019). Cognitive style and gender as predictors of students' academic performance in basic science and technology in MkpateEnin Local Government Area, Akwalbom State, Nigeria. *Kampala International University (KIU) Journal of Humanities*, 4(2), 151–159.
- Calsmith N. S. (2010). Gender differences in academic performance. *Journal of Experiment Psychology*, 6 (3), 44-50. Federal Ministry of Education, FME (2013). *National policy on education*, federal republic of Nigeria.
- Ghaffari , S. &Fatemi , M.A. (2016). The effects of using instructional conversation method on oral autonomy of iranian intermediate efl learners. *Theory and Practice in Language Studies*, 6 (6), 1191-1199.
- Giofre, D., Allen,K., Caviola, S., &Tffalini, E. (2022). The impasse on gender differences in intelligence: a meta-analysis on wise batteries.<https://doi.org/10.1007/s10698-022-09705-1>
- Girenton S. M. &Zucker, T. (2013). Instructional conversation in early childhood classrooms: *Policy Suggestions for Curriculum Standards and Professional Development Creative Education*, 4 (7), 60-68.
- Hendy, E & Cuevas, J. (2020). The Effects on Instructional Conversations on English Language Learners. *Georgia Educational Researcher: 17 (2)*. <https://digitalcommons.georgiasouthern.edu/gerjournal/vol17/iss2/5> investigation.<https://www.frontiersin.org/articles/10.3389/fpsyg.2019.01613/full>
- Kola, A.J. (2013). Analysis of gender performance in physics in colleges of education, Nigeria. *Journal of Education and Practice*, 4 (6). https://www.researchgate.net/publication/263651908_Analysis_of_Gender_Performance_in_Physics_in_Colleges_of_Education_Nigeria
- Maccoby, S. T. (2013) Gender conformity. *Journal of Science Education*, volume/number, 22-28.
- Murugesan, V. (2019). Innovations in teaching methods. *Journal of applied Science and computations*, 6 (1), 2588-2596.
- Olagunju, A.M. &Babayemi, J.O. (2014). Effect of crossword-picture puzzle teaching strategy and gender on students' achievement in basic science. *Journal of Education and Leadership Development*, 6(1), 43-54.
- Ouboumerrad, M. (2016). Teaching 21st century skills, and how to assess them. <https://www.dvv-international.de/en/adult-education-and-development/editions/aed-832016-skills-and-competencies/section-4-this-is-what-you-need/teaching-21st-century-skills-and-how-to-assess-them>
- Umanah, F.I. & Sunday, E.S. (2022). Crossword puzzle, flashcards teaching strategies and senior secondary school students' academic performance in Chemistry. *International Journal of Educational Benchmark (IJEb)*, 22 (2), 1-12.
- Zhang, J., Zhao, N. & Kong, O.P. (2019). The relationship between math anxiety and math performance: a meta-analytic